

Mechanisms of Cultural Capital Generation in Kashmir: Legacy of Maharaja Pratap Singh (1885-1925)

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Abstract

The proposed paper would try to situate the historical discourse of the Jammu and Kashmir region since late 19th to early 20th century in to a larger perspective as it has witnessed multiple parallel contesting strands which contextualized the socio-political cultural setting of the region. The reign of Maharaja Pratap Singh lasted for forty years (1885-1925). His reign has been acknowledged for initiating substantial innovative measures and modern infrastructural development of Jammu and Kashmir despite facing numerous obstacles. Further, under his leadership substantial progress was witnessed in facilitation of Indological research on Kashmir. The paper would highlight the literary contributions and its objectives during the said reign which shaped the region's Modern identity. These endeavours demonstrated Kashmir durbar's understanding of the mechanism of generation of mimetic capital.

Keywords

Indological Research, Literary Contributions, Mimetic Capital, Seat of Learning.

Introduction

The reign of Maharaja Pratap Singh lasted for forty years (1885-1925) with rather comprehensive reforms to almost every realm of social life. But has been pushed to the margins in the historical discourses and what he actually earned was the reproof of being sunk in lowest vices. [1]

However, despite facing numerous challenges, Maharaja Pratap Singh's reign (1885-1925) has been acknowledged for advancement in cultural and infrastructural development of the State. His leadership witnessed substantial progress in facilitation of Indological research on Kashmir. It was conducted with the establishment of the Archaeological and Research Department in 1904 and in 1911 respectively. Further, Kashmir Durbar's understanding of the mechanism of generation of mimetic capital was emphatically reflected through the inauguration of Kashmir Series of Text and Studies. Moreover, the strategy was evident in the presentation of Stain's catalogue of manuscripts to Cambridge University Library by his highness Maharajah Pratap Singh as an ambition to infiltrate the academic bastion of Europe.[2]

The literary legacy of this era and its objectives shaped the region's modern identity. The Imperial geo-political pragmatism, and increasingly widespread popular nationalist sentiment essentialized attack on the previous entitlement to sovereignty by virtue of decent and had to be complimented with ability to rule and more responsive service to the subjects. The pressure grew stronger for the control over the North Western boundaries of the empire more urgent than ever after 1878.[3]

Objective of study

The objective of the study is to explore and examine the cultural literary contributions of Maharajah Pratap Singh. His endeavours demonstrated Kashmir durbar's understanding of the mechanism of generation of mimetic capital which shaped the region's Modern identity.

Review of Literature

There is substantial literature available on the subject. Reviewing these works is crucial for creating a foundation for the proposed research article.

The work of Ananya J. Kabir, (2009), titled *Territory of Desire*, has blended literary, cultural elements of the region of Kashmir with historical analysis which provides valuable foundation for understanding how history became the site of political cultural contention in the modern era.

Another work by Chitralekha Zutshi (2014), titled *Kashmir's Contested Past*, is a historical grounded study of how Kashmir's past has been narrated through linguistic and cultural traditions from sixteen century to the present. Further, the exclusive monumental work compiled by George Grierson; (1932) *Dictionary of the Kashmiri Language*, remains one of the foundational references for Kashmiri language in linguistic scholarship provide insights on historical cultural studies of Kashmir. Another work titled *Lalla – Vakyani, A mystic Poetess of Ancient*

Kashmir, (1920) by George Grierson and Lionel Barnett are among the earliest extant works on Kashmiri poetic expressions shaping the language literary tradition of the region. Further, Hilton Knowles work on *Folktales of Kashmir*, (1888) is a classic collection of Kashmiri narratives of folk tales which reflects the thoughts and ways of the people of the region preserving Kashmiri oral tradition while offering insight in to cultural references and beliefs and values. Mohamad Saleem khan's work *The History of Jammu and Kashmir 1885-1925*, published by Gulshan Publishers (2024) is a comprehensive historical monograph covering the period of Maharaja Pratap Singh's reign which contributed to the regions' cultural and institutional development.

Further, Aseer W. M work; *Focus on Jammu and Kashmir(Rev.ed.)* , Crescent Publications , Jammu has dealt with the cultural legacy of Dogra rulers.

Main Text

Challenges

The appointment of Resident was called for both supervising administrative reforms and also obviate disturbances at the frontier, focussed on blocking Tzarist Russia which remained instrumental in deriving colonial interference in Kashmir.[4] In 1884 Viceroy Rippon argued for appointment of Resident in Kashmir for assisting and supervising administrative reforms. After the death of Ranbir Singh in 1885, British succeeded in forcing these terms on the new ruler Partap Singh, taking advantage of his political insecurity as Ranbir Singh was reluctant to name him as his successor.

These conditions were necessary prelude to the implementation of wide-ranging substantial reforms in the Princely State.[5] These included revenue reforms, reorganisation of army, improvement in judicial and State Administration, construction of roads etc. However, despite initiatives for multifarious reforms, the Maharaja was divested by the British government of all powers of governance and remained only titular chief of the state in 1889 that continued till 1905.[6]

He was accused of connivance with Tzarist Russia and plotting against the Resident in Kashmir.[7] The reign of Pratap Singh has witnessed, therefore a combination of challenges as well as marked by resilience and visionary reforms which laid the foundation of cultural enrichment, leaving an enduring legacy that was acknowledged globally.

Revamping Kashmir as Seat of Learning

In May 1904, the Government of Jammu and Kashmir Princely State resolved to create its own Archaeological and Research Department on the instructions of the Imperial authority. In 1910 Pratap Singh separated the Archaeology and Research department declaring it's objectives for revamping Kashmir as seat of learning as in the days of old Dogra Durbars. Efforts were directed to cordoning off this domain from British intervention. The Durbar attempted to guard the task of research and knowledge produced to serve the Dogra rulers to bolster their legitimacy as patrons of culture and learning. The research branch was placed under a separate hierarchy headed by linguist trained in Sanskrit and manned by Kashmiri pundits. It worked towards collecting, translating and publication of Sanskrit works[8].

In this way the Durbar attempted to guard the task of research and the knowledge produced from it. Though it traced its origin during the Ranbir Singh's reign. He fostered hindu learning through the establishment of Sanskrit library in Raghunath temple in Jammu which served as model for research Department.

Indological Research

Thus by 1911, to attain the declared objectives- production of memoires, guidebooks testimonials, collecting, translating and publishing Sanskrit texts were initiated. All played their part as does the Indological production of Grammer, dictionaries, critical editions, inventories of Sanskrit manuscript. The collective apparatus acted as privileged sites of pragmatics and strategy. These created the region as exceptional space and provided rationale for its national necessity.[9]

Further, Maharaja Pratap Singh's generous assistance to a crew of European enthusiasts and facilitation of Indological research on Kashmir arises question as to why would the Dogra princes be so forth coming in their help? The argument would be that it negotiated the extracting of legitimacy illustrated by work patronized by the maharajah in the Kashmir durbar's name.

It was conducted not merely in personal capacity but on behalf on his durbar – a structure and concept whose very existence derived from a complex set of colonial appropriation and indigenus re -appropriations for enactments of

sovereignty. The workings of this strategy of Maharaja confirmed and clarified the flourishing Indological scholarship on Kashmir. Further, through that scholarship attained external validation of his claim to the valley. The pundits whom he encouraged to share information with the European scholars were hailed by all concerned as vestiges of the ancient culture of Kashmir.[10]

Circle of Mutual Benefit

The European pursuits of antiquity thus locked the Dogra' rulers, the British administrators, the scholars and the pundits into a circle of mutual benefit. The circle soon widened to include other players. The creation, in 1898, of Srinagar Pratap Singh Museum on the premises of Ranbir Singh summer place already afford a preview of Dogra responses to European scholarly practices. It was to preserve and showcase the rich cultural tradition of Jammu Kashmir Baltistan and Gilgit.[11]

Kashmir Series of Text and Studies

Additionally, inauguration of Kashmir series of text and studies in 1911, published by Kashmir Durbar's Archaeological and Research Department, edited by its director J.C. Chatterjee, a Bengali brahmin, with a Cambridge education and printed at Nirnaya sager press in Bombay. was one such magnificent project.

That echoes the title format and vision and demonstrates Kashmir durbars shrewd understanding of the mechanism whereby value accrued through the infrastructure of academia – a phenomenon of academic capital. The title page was in both *Devnagari* and English and adorned with departmental stamp at the centre of which sat the Dogra crest. While its packaging and carefully planned dissemination signals durbar's decision to promote a certain brand of scholarship. [12]

Each volume of Kashmir series of Text and Studies was priced in sterling and rupees testifying international circulation and in anticipation pan European readership. This was an early ambition to infiltrate the academic bastion of Europe. The contents of the series exposed the connection between that promotion and Dogra ruler's self-fashioning as ruler of the State. The first volume was a critical edition of two Sanskrit handbooks of Saivism, the sutras of Vasu Gupta and *vimershini* by Khemraj. The photograph of the peak in the Pir panjal called the *harmukh* face of shiva that formed the cover page of the inaugural volume in the Kashmir series.[13]

In the preface Chatterjee has acknowledge the different pundits who had contributed to this task thereby refashioning standard Indological practice into a new collaboration that anticipates the utility of Kashmir for a vision of cultural mosaic of India.

From 1911 to 1960 Kashmir series of texts and studies comprised more than one hundred volumes. Initially all Sanskrit text from ancient Kashmir Shaivite philosophy were published and later text of other Indian philosophy were also added in this collection of texts. The Durbar had made effort to ensure the dissemination of the series. Pratap Singh's devotion of Swami Ram, a renowned *Trika* guru also prompted in setting up a machinery to collect and consolidate all scripts of Kashmir shiva philosophy as valuable treasure and heritage for posterity.[14]

Maharajah's research programme also procured a number of competent scholars like committed scholarship of Govind Kaul and Mukund Ram. In 1889, Pratap Singh declared Urdu as the court language and the language of administration thus officially ending the state patronage of Persian. As the Dogra state educational system replaced local *Makhtabs* and *Pathshalas* where Persian and Sanskrit education had been imparted even in rural areas. Persian linguistic and literary culture gradually lost its hold in Kashmir. While Kashmiri pundits who had been Persian scribes or Sanskrit scholars turned to learning English and assisting Orientalists in their Indological endeavours.[15]

Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscript

The famed Anglo-Hungarian Archaeologist and explorer- Sir Mark Aurel stain also acknowledged that it was Maharajah Pratap Singh, who supported for both the catalogue and the edition of Rajtarangini and the State Council given proof of their generous interest in it by sanctioning in 1891 a generous grant for the publication of the chronicle.

M.A Stain while accessing the treasure of Sanskrit manuscript of the Raghunath temple for the plan of cataloguing it, acknowledged the enlightened spirit of

Maharaja Pratap Singh who readily assent to the proposal of making the great collection formed by his father Ranbir Singh for research. Pratap Singh also used the similar strategy for its dissemination and presentation of the catalogue of manuscript to Cambridge University Library. The catalogue was also distributed to institutions of excellence, individual scholars in Europe and America. Further, the list also included Government officials, Institutions, Princes and Chiefs in India.

Between 1888 to 1900 more than 350 manuscripts from Kashmir collected and deposited at Oxford

University in 1911 that constituted the largest collection of Kashmiri Sanskrit Manuscript outside Kashmir.[16]

Further, the Archaeologist explorer later recruited as Resident of Kashmir-Fransis young husband, and the Settlement commissioner Walter Lawrence who wrote scholarly literature and popular accounts of valley's Histories, Geography, and Ethnography always thanked Pratap Singh and Amer Singh in their memoirs of the valley.

Literary Legacy

The reign of Pratap Singh also witnessed the completion of dictionary of Kashmiri language by great Irish linguist George Grierson, collaborated and assisted by Govind Kaul and Mukund Ram and Nityananda Shastri. Its completion was an arduous task which took almost 34 years of the dedicated scholarship of Grierson and the Kashmiri scholars. Orientalists' attempt to master the local language was taken up by Dr. Elmslie who authored the first vocabulary of Kashmiri language while delivering his duties as medical missionaries. T.R Wade's Grammar of Kashmiri language was the pioneering effort towards this project. [17]

Moreover, J.H. Knowles collected compendium of Kashmiri proverbs and folktales of Kashmir. Grierson and Lionel Barnet collected the sayings of mystic poetess of Kashmir -Lal Ded, and translated them for Asiatic society in 1896 and 1899. It finally appeared as Lallavakhyani in 1920. Grierson authored Two Volume dictionary of Kashmir and published technical essays on phonetics.[18]

Collaborations & Interactions

The effort and support of the Durbar in the literary pursuits and literary interactions also resulted in preparation of four volume commentary on *taiteriyā Upanishad* whose manuscript was preserved in Harvard university library USA. David Snodgrass, the American Scholar visited Kashmir and appreciated the support of the Durbar in the literary pursuits. Kashmir Epigraphical work was jointly prepared by Sten Konow and native scholar Mukund Ram. Jagadher Zadoo, a noted Sanskrit scholar worked with Japanese scholar Momo Moto kora who visited Srinagar in 1914 on Shivite text. Between 1914 and 1930, many Kashmiri texts like Kashmiri *Ramayan* and *Mahayana Prakash* were published by Asiatic society of Bengal. Moreover, in 1923 Kashmiri *Mahabharata* manuscript found a place of honour in the library of Prague University in Czechoslovakia.[19]

As consequences of the collaboration between Kashmir's Dogra Rulers and the British Empire, these scholarly investment in the valley as a source of Indic antiquity and its complicity with valleys tourism is also revealed, using Kashmiri multilingualism to illuminate the notion of Kashmiriyat. As the Self-conscious cultural text is bound by its own circumstances of production and consumption hence the prominence of regions antiquity had long lasting consequences on proper visualization of it.[20]

Conclusion

This collaboration between the Dogra maharajah of Jammu and Kashmir, the natives and European scholars' research laid the foundation of the regions antiquity that heightened the regions significance for post-colonial India. Hence, the interface of scholarship elevated Kashmir scholars to the level of world class researcher, exposed them in the international literary circle responsible for creating interest in the culture and wisdom of Kashmir all over the world. As a result, a new epoch and a new orientation in the enlargement of culture began during the reign of Pratap Singh.[21]

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